

Multiscale modeling for bottom-up prediction of failure parameters of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced composite lamina: from atoms to lamina-scale

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Introduction: CFRP

- Compared to metallic materials:**
- ✓ Superior specific strength and stiffness
 - ✓ Significant weight reduction benefits
- **Increasing adoption in the aerospace field**

*1 https://www.torayca.com/lineup/product/pro_001.html

*3 https://www.torayca.com/lineup/product/pro_003.html

*2 <https://stock.adobe.com/jp/>

*4 <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:787fuselage.jpg>

Introduction: Selection of matrix

Conventional matrix resin: epoxy resin

*2

エポキシ主剤

+

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Epoxy / curing agent reaction → 3D crosslinking

Functionality tailored by resin/curing agent selection

Environmental resistance / Flame retardancy / Moldability...

Matrix selection: A key design factor for CFRP

Introduction: Hierarchical structure of CFRP

Interactions across scales result in complex and coupled failure mechanisms

*1 https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Composite_laminate_specimen.JPG, Simon.white.1000

*2 M. Herrerez et al., *Composites Part A*, 2020, 129, 105691

Introduction: Hierarchical structure of CFRP

Objective:

CFRP strength parameters are estimated in a bottom-up manner through multiscale modeling, combining models specialized for each scale

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Target base resin / curing agent

Base resin

DGEBA

Curing agent

4,4'-DDS

DGEBA

DETA

TGDDM

4,4'-DDS

Three typical epoxy systems for aerospace applications are selected as case studies

Quantum chemical calculations

Energy profile of the crosslinking reaction

Reaction characteristics are specific to each material combination

→ Reaction pathways elucidated using the quantum chemical tool GRRM

Table 1

Activation energies, E_a , and heat of formation, H_f , obtained in GRRM.

Reaction type	E_a [kcal/mol]	H_f [kcal/mol]
DGEBA/4,4'-DDS		
Epoxy/primary amine	50.01	25.04
Epoxy/secondary amine	41.10	20.33
DGEBA/DETA		
Epoxy/primary amine	46.56	26.60
Epoxy/secondary amine (corner)	43.23	23.46
Epoxy/secondary amine (center)	46.68	22.15
TGDDM/4,4'-DDS		
Epoxy/primary amine	42.18	25.65
Epoxy/secondary amine (corner)	41.80	22.01

Molecular dynamics (MD): Curing simulation

Arrhenius-type reaction model

Base resin (DGEBA)

Curing agent
(DETA)

Reaction probability

$$p = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)$$

Heat of formation

$$E_{\text{Kin,after}} = E_{\text{Kin,before}} + H_f$$

**Curing simulated via MD with
explicit molecular structures
→ Resin model constructed**

MD : Numerical mechanical testing

Mechanical behavior of the resin model evaluated numerically

→ Obtained properties: **strength**, stiffness, **nonlinear response**, and CTE

MD : Resin strength estimation

Limitations of mechanical testing via MD

Simulation times (\sim ns) \rightarrow Extremely high strain rates
 \rightarrow **Strength tends to be significantly overestimated**

Strain-rate adjustment using Argon's theory of molecular chain buckling (Sundararaghavan and Kumar, *Int. J. Plasticity*, 2013)

MD : Resin strength estimation

Christensen's failure criteria:

$$3 \left(1 - \frac{T}{C} \right) \frac{\sigma_m}{C} + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{C} \right)^2 \leq \frac{T}{C}$$

(Christensen, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 2019)

Load is applied hydrostatically
→ von Mises stress is zero

$$\frac{T}{C} = \frac{3\sigma_m^f}{C + 3\sigma_m^f}$$

✱ T/C is strain-rate independent

As a result, the following strengths are obtained:

- ✓ **Strain-rate corrected compressive strength: C***
- ✓ **Brittle-ductile index: T/C**
- ✓ **Corrected tensile strength: T* = (T/C)·C***

MD : Resin nonlinear response

Elasto-viscoplastic constitutive law

(Kobayashi, *Transaction of JSME Series A*, 2004)

$$\dot{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}_m : \dot{\epsilon} - \frac{3\mu\dot{\epsilon}^p}{\bar{\sigma}} \sigma'$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}^p = \dot{\epsilon}_r \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma} + \beta\sigma_m}{g(\bar{\epsilon}^p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{k}}$$

$$g(\bar{\epsilon}^p) = g_1 (\bar{\epsilon}^p)^{g_2} + g_3$$

E_m , ν_m : Elastic parameter

g_1 , g_2 , g_3 : Plastic parameter

Plastic response obtained from MD is approximated by a constitutive model

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Microscopic FEA for UD lamina

Mechanical properties of UD lamina

- ✓ Transversely isotropic elasticity
- ✓ Plastic model considering hydrostatic pressure dependence
(Yokozeki et al., *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2007)
- ✓ Failure criterion for transversely isotropic materials
(Christensen, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 2013)

RVE analysis

(Okabe et al., *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, 2011)

Fiber kink theory

(Budiansky and Fleck, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, 1993)

*1

Spring element model

(Okabe et al., *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2005)

Other mechanical properties

*1 B. Budiansky, *Comput. Struct.*, 1983, 16(1), 3–12

Fiber-direction strength

Compressive

Tensile

Microscopic FEA for UD lamina

Resin properties from MD

E_m, ν_m

C

g_1, g_2, g_3

T/C

Homogenization techniques

(Suquet, 1987. *Lecture Notes in Physics*, 1987)

E_{LL}, E_{TT}, G_{LT}

ν_{LT}, ν_{TT}

Elastoplastic parameter identification using off-axis loading simulations

→ $a_{66}, A_1, n_1, A_2, n_2, \bar{\sigma}_{eff}^t$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{eff} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} [(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 2a_{44}\sigma_{23}^2 + 2a_{66}(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)] + a_1^2\sigma_{11}^2} + a_1(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}),$$

$$d\epsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{eff}}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\bar{\epsilon}_{eff}^p,$$

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{eff}^p = \begin{cases} A_1(\bar{\sigma}_{eff})^{n_1} & \text{if } \bar{\sigma}_{eff} \leq \bar{\sigma}_{eff}^t, \\ A_2(\bar{\sigma}_{eff})^{n_2} & \text{if } \bar{\sigma}_{eff} \geq \bar{\sigma}_{eff}^t, \end{cases}$$

Microscopic FEA for UD lamina

Christensen's failure criterion for transversely isotropic materials

(Christensen, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 2013)

$$\left(\frac{1}{T_{TT}} - \frac{1}{C_{TT}}\right)(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{T_{TT}C_{TT}}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{S_{TT}^2}(\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{S_{LT}^2}(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2) \leq 1$$

Simulating resin failure in composite materials

$$\left(\frac{1}{T_{LL}} - \frac{1}{C_{LL}}\right)\sigma_{11} + \frac{1}{T_{LL}C_{LL}}\sigma_{11}^2 \leq 1$$

$$S_{TT}^2 = \left(\frac{1 + \frac{T_{TT}}{C_{TT}}}{3 + 5\frac{T_{TT}}{C_{TT}}}\right) T_{TT}C_{TT}$$

$T_{TT}, C_{TT}, S_{LT}, C_{LL}, T_{LL}$

Resin properties from MD

E_m, ν_m C

g_1, g_2, g_3 T/C

Fibre direction compressive strength

Budiansky's fiber kink theory

(Budiansky and Fleck, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, 1993)

Fiber direction tensile strength

Spring element model

(Okabe et al., *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 2005)

Mathematical model for failure prediction considering:

- ✓ Probabilistic fracture of individual fibers
- ✓ Shear stress transfer to broken fibers

Estimated material properties

Epoxy resin material properties from MD

	C		T/C	
	MD	Experiment	MD	Experiment
DGEBA/4,4'-DDS	180 MPa	142 MPa	0.670	0.714
DGEBA/DETA	134 MPa	101 MPa	0.657	0.700
TGDDM/4,4'-DDS	247 MPa	207 MPa	0.603	0.544

UD lamina material properties

	Young's modulus		Poisson's ratio		Shear modulus
	E_{LL}	E_{TT}	ν_{LT}	ν_{TT}	G_{LT}
DGEBA/4,4'-DDS	162 GPa	6.12 GPa	0.230	0.397	3.20 GPa
DGEBA/DETA	162 GPa	4.92 GPa	0.231	0.389	2.43 GPa
TGDDM/4,4'-DDS	162 GPa	6.15 GPa	0.226	0.387	3.26 GPa

※ T800S carbon fiber is assumed

Estimated material properties

Plastic behavior of each composite material

	a_{66}	A_1	n_1	A_2	n_2	$\bar{\sigma}_{\text{eff}}^t$
DGEBA/4,4'-DDS	2.59	1.28×10^{-12}	4.24	3.10×10^{-19}	7.25	159 MPa
DGEBA/DETA	2.56	2.13×10^{-11}	3.91	3.16×10^{-17}	6.74	115 MPa
TGDDM/4,4'-DDS	2.64	7.39×10^{-13}	4.23	2.09×10^{-17}	6.21	201 MPa

Estimated material properties

Five strengths of each composite material

	T_{TT}	C_{TT}	S_{LT}	C_{LL}	T_{LL}
DGEBA/4,4'-DDS	69 MPa	150 MPa	63 MPa	1157 MPa	2888 MPa
DGEBA/DETA	49 MPa	109 MPa	47 MPa	863 MPa	2894 MPa
TGDDM/4,4'-DDS	74 MPa	187 MPa	81 MPa	1254 MPa	2846 MPa

Experimental strengths of similar materials

	$T_{TT} *1$	$C_{TT} *1$	$S_{LT} *2$	$C_{LL} *3$	$T_{LL} *1$
T800S/3900-2B	67 MPa	193 MPa	119 MPa	1242 MPa	3100 MPa

*1 Morimoto et al., *JAXA advanced composites database*, 2018

*2 Raju and Acosta, *Crashworthiness of composite fuselage structures*, 2010

*3 Yokozeki et al., *Composites Part A*, 2006

Summary and Applications

- ✓ In this study, **five composite strength** parameters were estimated in a bottom-up manner by integrating **quantum chemical calculations**, molecular dynamics (**MD**), finite element analysis (**FEA**), and **theoretical models**.
- ✓ The seamless linkage of these methods enables both bottom-up and top-down analyses, clarifying the correlation between microscopic **molecular structure** and **macroscopic strength**.
- ✓ The five obtained strength parameters can be applied to **laminates-scale analyses**, such as open hole tension (OHT) and compression (OHC) simulations.

$$\begin{matrix} E_{LL}, E_{TT}, G_{LT} & a_{66}, A_1, n_1 \\ \nu_{LT}, \nu_{TT} & \bar{\sigma}_{\text{eff}}^t, A_2, n_2 \\ T_{TT}, C_{TT}, S_{LT} \\ C_{LL} & T_{LL} \end{matrix}$$

Open hole compression